

Project research report:
"Development of a methodology for monitoring marine diesel engines in real time with the aim of increasing energy and environmental efficiency using non-destructive testing methods"

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on the results of the study on the uniformity of fuel supply in a ship's diesel generator using the acoustic emission non-destructive testing method.

Research location:
RTU Institute of Aeronautics, Space Engineering and Transport
Riga.

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1. Introduction

A modern ship is a complex technical system, the failures of which can be associated with various factors: technological defects, operational wear or adverse external conditions [1]. The main condition for reducing the probability of failure due to technical reasons is to increase the operational reliability of the ship's power equipment. In this context, the determining factor is the operational reliability of the diesel engine, which in some cases accounts for up to 45% of all technical failures [2].

Existing automatic, control, monitoring and regulation systems for marine diesel engines are unable to fully take into account technological errors in the manufacture of engine parts, as well as changes in the technical condition of the fuel equipment (FA) during long-term operation [3]. As a result, problems arise in diagnostics, assessment of technical condition and regulation methodology, which is necessary to ensure stable operational indicators throughout the entire engine service life. There is also a lack of scientifically sound methods for calculating and theoretical analysis of operational parameters that would take into account the above factors.

Acoustic emission (AE) method is an effective tool for monitoring various technological processes, as well as changes in the structure and state of materials [4]. The high sensitivity of this method to developing defects allows them to be identified at an early stage, to assess their danger and rate of development. Previous studies have also proven the effectiveness of the AE method in the mechanical engineering and energy industries [5]. Therefore, the use of this method in diesel engine fuel system diagnostics is of particular interest, which could significantly expand diagnostic capabilities in fuel supply and valve systems.

Of particular note is the contribution of the non-destructive testing (NDT) research group of the Institute of Aeronautics, Space Engineering and Transport of Riga Technical University (RTU), which in recent years has actively developed the practical application of the AE method in ship and aircraft engine diagnostics. Their work includes the development of diagnostic algorithms, the adaptation of sensor technologies to complex operating conditions, and the mathematical modeling of operating parameters [6].

Diagnostics, prevention and repair of diesel fuel equipment (high-pressure fuel pump and injectors) allow for timely identification and elimination of problems that cause excessive fuel consumption or unstable engine operation [7]. Statistically, up to 70% of failures in diesel units are directly related to high-pressure fuel equipment [8]. Calculations show that a diesel engine of a heavy vehicle consumes an average of 2–3 tons of fuel per year and increases harmful emissions into the atmosphere: CO by 100–150 kg and CH by 30–50 kg [9]. Regular diagnostics and timely maintenance allow for reducing fuel losses and extending engine service life by 15–20% [10].

Normal operation of the fuel system valve mechanism ensures continuous fuel supply and high-quality atomization into the cylinder, which directly affects engine power and economy [11]. By timely detection and elimination of malfunctions of only one nozzle (for example, de-coking, flushing, grinding or pressure adjustment of the nozzle), it is possible to save 10–15 kg of fuel for every 10 thousand km of mileage [12].

The aim of the research is to scientifically substantiate and develop methods and means for improving the economic and ecological performance of marine diesel engines. This includes the improvement of fuel supply and mixture formation processes, ensuring the stability of fuel supply system parameters and its operational diagnostics during operation. *deves sistēmas parametru stabilitātes nodrošināšanu un tās operatīvu diagnostiku ekspluatācijas laikā.*

Acoustic diagnostics of the engine fuel system

Study of the engine sound can provide an idea of the wear of individual units and assemblies. Certain mechanical noises indicate the technical condition of the power unit [1]. Normal operation of the fuel equipment is characterized by continuous fuel supply and its high-quality spraying into the cylinder, which determines the engine power and economy [2].

Monitoring of the fuel equipment operation is limited to preventive actions (flushing the fuel system), inspections and adjustments [3]. Visual inspection of the external surface of the object is allowed at a pressure not exceeding PPACЧ (calculated pressure) [4].

Research methodology

The study used the AE method, within the framework of which the piezo transducer (PAE) was installed on the engine fuel system in idle mode, and AE signals were recorded [5]. In this way, the initial state was fixed, after which controlled changes were introduced in the fuel supply operation. The results obtained were analyzed to identify the sources of acoustic signals.

The acoustic method for unit diagnostics has not yet been fully developed, and significant theoretical and experimental studies are still needed [6].

Acoustic Emission Control (AEC)

Standards – AEC was performed in accordance with the European standard EN14584:2013, which regulates the performance of AEC for pressure vessels and other technical objects [7].

Objective – The main objective of AEC was to determine the AE sources and their coordinates related to the uniformity of fuel supply to the injectors from the high-pressure fuel pump [8].

Adjustment – In case active AE sources were identified, fuel equipment adjustment was performed at their locations to ensure uniform fuel supply. Incorrect valve operation can cause compression problems, loss of power, unstable engine operation and increased fuel consumption [9].

Commonly encountered problems:

Incomplete fuel combustion – if the valve clearances are inadequate, the fuel will not burn completely, which worsens fuel economy and increases harmful emissions [10].

Increased fuel consumption – due to incomplete valve operation, the fuel will not burn efficiently enough, which increases fuel consumption and negatively affects the environment [11].

Corrective measures – Based on the results of the AEK, the necessary corrective measures are determined to ensure a full and safe operating condition [12]

2. Research object

The study adopted a diesel generator type (Ship diesel generator 4Ч 8.5/11, 16 kW) with the AE method.

Ship diesel generator 4Ч 8.5/11, 16 kW

- Type: 4 – 8.5/11
- Factory number: 7609400
- Number of cylinders: 4

Indicators 5Д4 (4Ч8.5/11):

- Power, kW: nominal 19.1; standard 20.25
- Number of revolutions, min⁻¹: 1500
- Specific consumption, g/kW h:
 - for fuel: at nominal power – 260, at standard power – 245
 - for oil (for losses) – 1.5
- Estimated resource, thousand h:
 - until the first inspection - 7
 - until the capital repair - 16
- Overall dimensions, mm:
 - length L – 920

- width B – 610
- height H – 970
- Mass (dry), kg: 355
- Fuel: diesel fuel (ГОСТ 305—82)
- Oil: M-10Г2К, M-10Г2 (ГОСТ 8581-78), M-10B2C, M-10Г2ЦС (ГОСТ 12337-84)

Application

Intended for operating generators, compressors, pumps, ship propellers and other mechanisms whose required power corresponds to the power of a diesel engine.

Appearance

Fig. 1. Appearance of a diesel generator

Design

The cylinder block-crankcase is made of cast iron with replaceable wet cast-iron cylinder liners. Bearings for the crankshaft and camshaft are mounted in its transverse walls. The block-crankcase of the four-cylinder diesel engines of both sizes is split; its lower part serves as the oil sump and reservoir for lubricating oil.

Each cylinder is equipped with one intake and one exhaust valve, as well as a pre-combustion swirl chamber insert.

The pistons, stamped from an aluminum alloy, have three compression rings and one oil scraper ring of box type with a spiral expander; the upper compression ring is chromium-plated. The pistons are cooled with lubricating oil supplied from the internal cavity of the crankshaft through holes in the connecting rods. The piston pins are hollow, floating type. The connecting rods are stamped, I-beam shaped, with an oblique split in the crank end.

The crankshaft is made as a solid forging from alloy steel; the journals are hardened by high-frequency induction, and the main bearings are roller-type.

The valves are actuated by tappets, pushrods, and rocker arms driven from the camshaft located in the engine's block-crankcase. The camshaft also carries cams for driving the fuel pump.

On the diesel engine (4Ch8.5/11) designed for generator drive, a single-mode centrifugal direct-acting governor with adjustable degree of irregularity and a resiliently connected dashpot is installed. The fuel system includes a fuel feed pump with a manual priming mechanism, a fuel filter, a high-pressure fuel pump, injectors, and pipelines.

The full-flow lubrication system includes a mesh strainer, a gear pump, an oil filter, safety and relief valves, a remote pressure gauge and thermometer, and an oil level indicator.

The cooling system is combined: the cylinder liners are cooled by a thermosiphon system, while the cylinder heads are cooled by forced circulation with a centrifugal pump. The coolant outlet temperature is maintained by a bellows-type thermostat.

The intake system uses an oil-bath inertia air filter. Exhaust gases are discharged through the exhaust manifold. The diesel is started by an electric starter.

Fuel Supply System

The engine fuel system consists of a feed pump, a filter, a high-pressure fuel pump, injectors, and pipelines. The feed pump is piston-type, supplying fuel at a pressure of 1–1.5 kg/cm², and is mounted directly on the high-pressure fuel pump housing.

The engine's fuel system is equipped with a felt filter, and each injector has a slot-type filter.

The high-pressure fuel pump is of the block type. Fuel delivery is regulated by changing the end of delivery through rotation of the plunger, which has a helical cut-off edge on its cylindrical surface. The drive shaft of the block-type high-pressure fuel pump is connected to the engine camshaft via gears, and to the camshaft of the fuel pump via a flexible coupling.

The valve mechanism is the direct actuating mechanism of the gas distribution system, ensuring timely supply of the fuel-air mixture to the engine cylinders and subsequent exhaust gas removal. The key elements of the system are the valves, which must also ensure sealing of the combustion chamber.

Fig. 2. Four-plunger fuel pump 4Ch 8.5/11; The valve mechanism is the main actuating component of the valve timing system (gas distribution mechanism) of a modern internal combustion engine (ICE). This unit is responsible for the precise operation of the engine and ensures its proper functioning during operation

3. Research conditions

AE Equipment Used for the Study

1. Physical Acoustics Pocket AE-2 (USA)
2. AE System AMSY-6 Vallen Systeme (Germany)
3. Acoustic Emission Complex PAC-3000/3104 (USA)
4. Acoustic Emission Device AF-15 (Moldova)

AE Evaluation Criteria

The evaluation criteria depend on the test object and the type of location:

- For planar arrangement of AE sources:
LVS EN 14584 – Section 8: Interpretation of Results
- For zonal arrangement of AE sources:
LVS EN 12817 – Annex C.5: Data Evaluation and Analysis
- For pressure vessels for liquefied petroleum gas with a volume greater than 13 m³:
LVS EN 12819 – Annex C.6: Data Evaluation and Analysis
- For leak detection:
LVS EN ISO 18081 – Section 11: Data Interpretation
- For refillable seamless steel gas cylinders and tubes:
LVS EN ISO 16148 – Section 10: Real-Time Evaluation Criteria

- For fiber-reinforced polymers:
LVS EN 15857 – Sections: 7.3.5 Evaluation Criteria, 7.3.6 Stopping Criteria, 8 Interpretation of AE Results/Underlying Mechanisms

Classification System for AE Sources

1. Criteria selected for the AE study of the given object. The justification for the choice of specific criteria and their values is provided. The classification of AE sources and operator actions during the registration of an AE source of a particular class are described.
2. **Amplitude criterion:**
 - Class 1 single passive AE sources (minor AE sources on AE charts have a random nature and low amplitudes).
 - Class 2 single passive AE sources (minor AE sources on AE charts also have a random nature and low amplitudes).
3. **Continuous AE criterion:**
 - Registration of continuous AE, the level of which exceeds the system threshold. According to the continuous AE criterion, the situation is classified as Class I (absence of continuous AE) – minor AE sources.

AE Testing Methodology (AEC)

AE testing of the fuel equipment was carried out on an engine operating at idle speed, maintained for 1 minute in order to register possible AE phenomena detectable by the AE equipment.

Sensors of two PAC Pocket AE-2 systems (2 units) and four sensors of the AMSY-6 Vallen Systeme were simultaneously mounted using CIATIM-221 contact grease and attached to the injectors. AE systems PAC-3000 and AF-15 were used with one sensor each, installed sequentially starting from the injector of the first cylinder.

After installation, the AE systems were switched on, and calibration of AE channels was carried out using the *Su-Nielsen method* and on test specimen No. 18AE (see Fig. 3).

Calibration of AE Systems on Test Specimen No. 18AE

An acoustic emission signal simulator (AE signal calibrator) is a device designed to generate elastic oscillations (waves) simulating acoustic emission signals in the test object.

Fig. 3 test sample No. 18ae

Method	Acoustic Emission
Sample Type	Pipe fragment
Material	Stainless steel 12X18H10T
Geometric Dimensions	Ø 60 × 2.5 mm, Length 432 mm
Industrial Sectors	1, 2, 3
Product Sectors	wp
Regulatory Documents	EN 1330-9, EN 13554, EN 14584, EN 13477-1, EN 13477-2
Control Parameters	Simulation of AE sources
Location Type	Linear
Source Classification (by hazard level)	According to EN 14584: A1 = 90 dB; A2 = 100 dB; N1 = 3; N2 = 10

Table 1.

Simulation parameters and detected AE sources in the test specimen

Simulator placement coordinates (see Fig. 3a), mm		Type of AE source	AE source class	Coordinates of the detected AE source, mm	
x	y			x	y
140	-	descrete	2 (active)	142 ± 5	-

Note:

Permissible errors in determining the coordinates of the AE source are established based on values obtained by Level 3 specialists during inspection.

Instructions for AE control

Sample No.	<i>18AЭ</i>
Product (name of the test object, description, or sketch)	<i>Pipe fragment</i>
Geometric dimensions	<i>∅ 60 × 2,5 mm, length 432 mm</i>
Material grade	<i>stainless steel 12Kh18N10T</i>
Test scope	<i>100 %</i>
Industrial sector/product sector	<i>1, 2, 3 / wp</i>
Test objective	<i>Detection of AE sources in the test object</i>
Regulatory documents	<i>EN 1330-9, EN 13554, EN 14584, EN 13477-1, EN 13477-2</i>
Personnel requirements	<i>Level 2 specialists in the AT method, certified in the ISO 9712 system</i>
Test instruments and equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acoustic emission system signal cable lines - AE transducers - Load simulator holders (voltage source) - Measuring tape – 3 m - Roughness sample Ra 6.3 - Litol-24 contact medium
Instrument setup and preparation for testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equipment performance check PAE - assessment of surface roughness at sensor installation locations (no worse than Ra 6.3) - determination of the acoustic properties of the test object (attenuation) - creation of a PAE placement diagram - creation of a loading program

Условия контроля

Test parameters:

- test type	<u><i>Load simulation</i></u>
- working environment	<u><i>air</i></u>
- object temperature	<u><i>from +16 to +25 °C</i></u>
- ambient temperature	<u><i>from +16 to +25 °C</i></u>
- loading device type	<u><i>load simulator</i></u>
- test pressure	<u><i>25 kgf/cm² (2,2MPa)</i></u>

Loading schedule parameters:

- loading rate	<u><i>5 kgf/cm²/min (0.5 MPa/min)</i></u>
- holding time	<u><i>1 - 3 min</i></u>
- load values during holding time	<u><i>2.0, 2.2, 2.0 MPa</i></u>

Equipment operating modes:

- Preamplifier gain	<u><i>34 dB</i></u>
- Main gain by channel	<u><i>0 dB</i></u>
- Channel discrimination level	<u><i>36 dB</i></u>
- Input-referred noise level	<u><i>5 mkV</i></u>
- Operating frequency band	<u><i>50-500 kHz</i></u>

Calibration of AE Equipment Using a Hsu-Nielsen Source

Hsu-Nielsen Simulator and Electronic AE Signal Simulator

1 – Pencil, 2 – Guide Ring, 3 – Graphite Rod.

Graphite – 2 h; Diameter – 0.5 mm (alternatively – 0.3 mm);

Length 3.0 ± 0.5 mm

Fig. 4. Su-Nielsen simulator, 1 – pencil, 2 – guide ring, 3 – graphite rod

Purpose

- Verifying the operability of the AE system;
- Calibrating acoustic emission transducers (AETs);
- Determining the propagation velocity and attenuation of elastic vibrations;
- Verifying the correctness of the AE system's calculation of the location coordinates of acoustic emission sources immediately before testing.

Before testing, the proper functioning of all sensors and measuring instruments was verified using a Hsu-Nielsen source at a fixed distance from each sensor. This distance was chosen to avoid saturation. The amplitude of the H-N test at a distance of 5 cm from the center of the sensor is 71 dB AE.

Fig. 5. Testing the portable AE system Pocket AE- using a Su-Nielsen source

Processing and Presentation of AE Test Results

1. AE data processing and analysis were performed using specialized software from the Physical Acoustics Pocket AE system and the AMSY-6 Vallen System AE system.
2. Primary processing of the RAS-3000/3104 system's AE and the AF-15 device's AE was performed directly during testing based on an analysis of AE parameter changes.

A diesel generator diagram showing the fuel system components for testing fuel flow uniformity.

Cylinder numbering is as follows: from the radiator (1, 2, 3, 4), see Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Engine diagram with fuel system elements indicated for research

a)

b)

Fig. 7. Calibration of the device (thickness gauge)

a) Determining engine temperature $T=45^{\circ}\text{C}$ b) Calibration of the device

Fig. 8. Measuring the thickness of the valve cover coating

Fig. 9. Installation of sensors on the valve cover of the cylinder block

Fig. 10. Checking for signals from sensors

4. Conducting research using the acoustic emission method

4.1. STAGE I

Research using AE equipment – “Pocket AE-2”

The product's condition was assessed using acoustic emission testing (AE) using a portable two-channel Physical Acoustics Pocket AE instrument (Fig. 11), a piezoelectric sensor, and a Physical Acoustics Corporation IL-LP-WS external preamplifier with a bandwidth of 100–1000 kHz. A single channel with a discrimination level of +23 dB and a sampling rate of 1 MSPS was used for testing.

Fig. 11. Pocket AE-2 kit. Inventory No. 8520232001

The piezoelectric transducer recording the acoustic emission signal was attached to the overpressure valve during the experiment. Acoustic contact between the device and the sensor was ensured by grease and mechanically secured.

AE Equipment Settings

The following Physical Acoustics Pocket AE equipment settings were used for the acoustic emission analysis:

- 2 channels;
- sensitivity spread: ± 1.5 dB;
- AE signal gain: 26 dB;
- frequency range: 100 - 500 kHz;
- noise amplitude discrimination (cutoff) threshold: 36 dB.
- post-processing filtering: extreme values are ignored by default.

Stage 1

Test time: 15 hours 10 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №1

Sensor №2 – installed on the injector of cylinder №4

a)

b)

Fig. 12. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 1; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 1

Stage 2

Test time: 15 hours 13 minutes

One sensor is installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №4

a)

b)

Fig. 13. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 2; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 2

Stage 3

Test time: 15 hours 17 minutes

One sensor is installed on the injectors

Sensor №2 is installed on the injector of cylinder №1

a)

b)

Fig. 14. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 3; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 3

Stage 4

Test time: 15 hours 26 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №2

Sensor №2 – installed on the injector of cylinder №3

a)

b)

Fig. 15. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 4; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 4

Stage 5

Test time: 15 hours 32 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injector and fuel pump.

Sensor №1 is installed on the injector of cylinder №3.

Sensor №2 is installed on the fuel pump.

a)

b)

Fig. 16. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 5; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 5

Stage 6

Sensors are installed on the fuel line and on the fuel pump housing.

Sensor №1 is installed on the fuel line of cylinder №4.

Sensor №2 is installed on the fuel pump housing.

a)

b)

Fig. 17. a) Photo of the sensor installation stage 6; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 6

Sensor Installation Diagram, Stage 6

Stage 6.1

Test time: 15 hours 39 minutes; Both sensors are on

Stage 6.2

Test time: 15 hours 44 minutes; Only sensor №2 is on

Stage 6.3

Test time: 15 hours 49 minutes; Only sensor №1 is on

Acoustics Pocket AE Parameter Graphs

Acoustic emission signal waveforms obtained during one full cycle and the first quarter of the following cycle by a sensor mounted on the body of injector №1.

The ranges from 0 to 0.02 and 0.125 to 0.145 represent the signal from injector №1; the range from 0.03 to 0.045 represents the signal from injector №3; the range from 0.06 to 0.08 represents the signal from injector №4; and the range from 0.09 to 0.11 represents the signal from injector №2.

Fig. 18. Acoustic emission signal from injector №1

The waveform of the acoustic emission signals obtained during one full and the first quarter of the next cycle by the sensor installed on the body of injector №2

Fig. 19. Acoustic emission signal from injector №2

The waveform of the acoustic emission signals obtained during one full and the first quarter of the next cycle by the sensor installed on the body of injector №3

Fig. 20. Acoustic emission signal from injector №3

The waveform of the acoustic emission signals obtained during one full and the first quarter of the next cycle by the sensor installed on the body of injector №4

Fig. 21. Acoustic emission signal from injector №4

Acoustic emission signal waveforms obtained during the experiment. When the engine is idling, the main source of AE is the difference in pulse signals, indicating uneven fuel delivery to cylinders 2 and 3.

4.2. STAGE II

Research using the AE system – “VALLEN SYSTEME”

VALLEN SYSTEM (Germany). A European manufacturer of AE systems. They have been producing systems since the 1980s. Their latest development, the AMSY-6 digital AE system, is a multi-channel AE system consisting of parallel, fully synchronized measurement channels. Each channel includes an analog measurement unit, a digital signal processing unit, and a communication unit with a control hardware and software module with a full set of peripherals. AMSY-6 AE System Vallen Systeme (Germany)

Main technical specifications:

AE event recording rate: 140,000 AE events/sec, with full customization of collected data, filtering, time sorting, and hard disk recording.

Waveform processing speed (TR functions): waveform recording over 40 MB/sec, with full customization of collected data, filtering, time sorting, and hard disk recording.

Real-time processing of AE parameters, 40 MHz ADC frequency, 16 bits per channel.

Up to 8 parametric channels can be used.

Fig. 22. AE system AMSY-6 Vallen System (Germany)

The 8-channel AE recording and system, ID #48767 AMSY-6 model MB6, is an acoustic emission system that fully complies with EN13477-1, “Non-destructive testing – Acoustic emission testing – Equipment characterization – Part 1: Equipment description.”

AE Equipment Settings

The following VallenSysteme AMSY-6 AE equipment settings were used for the AE testing: 4 channels,

- sensitivity spread: ± 3 dB;
- AE signal gain: 36.1 dB (AMSY-6), - frequency range: 95 - 500 kHz (AMSY-6),
- amplitude discrimination (cutoff) threshold: 36 dB.
- duration control interval (SCETO): 2000 μ s.
- dead time: 500 μ s.
- Maximum duration - 3000 μ s.
- Pre-filtering
- Post-processing filtering - Extreme values are ignored by default.

a)

b)

Fig. 23. a) AE system AMSY-6 Vallen System (Germany); b) AE sensor VS-150-RSC

Test object
Marine diesel generator

Type: 4 - 8.5/11
 Serial number: 7609400
 Number of cylinders: 4

a)

b)

Fig. 24. a) Marine diesel generator; b) engine diagram showing fuel system components for research

Stage 1 Measurement

Test time: 15 hours 56 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №1

Sensor №2 – installed on the injector of cylinder №4

a)

b)

Fig. 25. Stage 1; a) Marine diesel generator; b) engine diagram showing fuel system components for research

Stage 2 Measurement

Test time: 16 hours 10 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №2

Sensor №2 – installed on the injector of cylinder №3

a)

b)

Fig. 26. Stage 2; a) Marine diesel generator; b) engine diagram showing fuel system components for research

Stage 3 Measurement

Test time: 16 hours 28 minutes

Sensors are installed on the injectors

Sensor №1 – installed on the injector of cylinder №1

Sensor №2 – installed on the injector of cylinder №2

Sensor №3 – installed on the injector of cylinder №3

Sensor №4 – installed on the injector of cylinder №4

a)

b)

Fig. 27. Stage 2; a) Marine diesel generator; b) engine diagram showing fuel system components for research

Graphs of AE parameters from the VallenSysteme ANSY6 system:

Fig. 28. a) The waveform of the pulse from the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №1 at the moment of injection; b) Pulse spectrum of the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №1 at the moment of injection

Fig. 29. a) The waveform of the pulse from the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №2 at the moment of injection; b) Pulse spectrum of the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №2 at the moment of injection

Fig. 30 a) The waveform of the pulse from the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №3 at the moment of injection; b) Pulse spectrum of the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №3 at the moment of injection

Fig. 31 a) The waveform of the pulse from the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №4 at the moment of injection; b) Pulse spectrum of the acoustic emission sensor attached to injector №4 at the moment of injection

Based on their signal shape, AE types are classified as discrete, which corresponds to processes that generate a sudden increase in load and the presence of a large number of low-amplitude AE sources. The pulse waveform and spectrum of acoustic emission signals were obtained during the experiment. When the engine is idling, the main source of AE is the difference in pulse signals, indicating uneven fuel delivery to the 2nd and 3rd cylinders.

The study utilized serial AF-15 devices and the RAS 3000 system. To obtain comparable results, calibration and verification of the acoustic coupling between the transducers and the test object were performed. The following AE parameters were recorded during preliminary measurements:

- amplitude;
- energy;
- total count;
- mathematical expectation.

AE data was collected simultaneously by the PAC-3000/3104, AF-15, and a computer system. "POISK-1B" was used to compare the readings of PAC-3000/3104 and AF-15.

4.3. STAGE III

Research using the PAC-3000/3104 acoustic emission system

It is designed for the same purposes as the AF-15 and POISK-1B devices, but has broader capabilities for processing AE data.

The system consists of a PAC-3104 four-channel section for recording AE data and a PAC-3000 computer section for collecting, processing, and analyzing nine AE parameters. The two sections are connected via a PAC-3000 interface cable.

The PAC-3000 system includes four R15 sensors and four 1220 A PUs.

The computer section of the system is equipped with a pulsar that emits AE signals of a precisely defined power with a variable frequency, sending these signals into the sample for self-testing of the entire system.

AE equipment settings

The AEKAL-2 calibrator is used for calibrating the RAS-3000 system. It generates single radio pulses similar to AE signals with varying leading edge shapes and pulse fill rates.

The system allows the sampling level (threshold level) of AE signals to be adjusted up to 10.0 V in 0.1 V increments.

The control unit is capable of filtering signals using high-pass and low-pass filters and adjusting the gain by 40 or 60 dB. The control unit's intrinsic noise level is no more than 2 μV . Gain adjustment in 1 dB increments (up to 60 dB) is performed in the main amplifier. The main amplifier also features removable filters, allowing the device's bandwidth to be adjusted over a wide range from 20 to 2000 kHz.

Fig. 32 Acoustic emission system PAC 3000

Number of channels	4
Total AE count, pulses	10^0 - 10^6
AE count rate, pulses/s	10^0 - 10^6
Total AE pulse count, pulses	10^0 - 10^3
Dynamic range of AE signal amplitude recording, mV	155-4950
Amplification path operating frequency range, kHz	20-1000
High-pass filter cutoff frequency, kHz	700
Low-pass filter cutoff frequency, kHz	200
Signal attenuation by filters, dB/octave	>20
Main amplifier gain, dB	
max	60
min	10
Gain setting resolution, dB	1
Preamplifier gain, dB, minimum	40
Clock pulse repetition period, selectable	10, 30
Sweep generator period, selectable	10 s, 1 min, 1 h, 8 h

Fig. 33 Graphs of AE parameters from the PAC 3000 system; a) 4th cylinder; b) 3rd cylinder; c) 2nd cylinder; d) 1st cylinder

When the engine is idling, most of the acoustic signals correspond to friction between the throttle body's faces. Due to its small size, the amplitude of the resulting acoustic emission pulses does not exceed 50 dB (Fig.). As the friction progresses, a decrease in intensity is observed, and the main source of acoustic emission becomes the development of pulsed signals, indicating uneven fuel delivery to cylinders 2 and 3.

4.4. STAGE IV

Research using the acoustic emission system AF – 15 (Moldova).

Measuring equipment type, instrument model:

AF-15, Ch3-33 (see Appendix 1), PAC AECAL-2, DT-830B.

The equipment being tested and used during the test include AE transducers with mounting devices and materials to ensure acoustic coupling with the test object; AE signal simulators; electronic units designed to amplify and process AE signals; and computing equipment for processing and presenting test results.

Acoustic emission equipment permanently installed at the test object does not provide real-time processing and display of information, nor does it process, display, and output accumulated test data to documentation devices.

The test was conducted according to the diagram (see Appendix 2).

The device is designed to study and monitor the mechanical properties of various objects (samples of structural materials, pressure vessels, machine parts and assemblies, etc.) using AE signal parameters. The device provides reception of AE signals via two channels and simultaneous recording of at least four informative parameters: amplitude, count rate, sum of oscillations, activity, sum of events, difference in arrival time (linear location), shape and duration of the AE pulse.

AE equipment settings

The device's bandwidth ranges from 20 to 2000 kHz and allows for high-pass filter cutoff frequencies in the ranges of 20, 200, 500, and 1000 kHz, and low-pass filter cutoff frequencies of 200, 500, 1000, and 2000 kHz.

The built-in AE signal amplifier has a gain of -60 dB with 1 dB adjustment.

The device includes a calibrator subunit for calibrating the device before operation, and an AE signal simulator for tuning the AE path.

a)

b)

Fig. 34. a) AE system АФ-15, ЧЗ-33 и ПАЭФ-014 с GT-200; b) AE sensor GT-200

Number of channels	2
Total AE count, imp.	10^0-10^6
AE count rate, pulses/s	10^0-10^6
Total AE pulse count, pulses	10^0-10^3
AE activity, pulses/s	10^0-10^3
AE signal amplitude dynamic range, mV	155-4950
Amplification path operating frequency range, kHz	19-2184
High-pass filter cutoff frequency, kHz	17, 174, 450, 843
Low-pass filter cutoff frequency, kHz	216, 538
Filter signal attenuation, dB/octave	>24
Main amplifier gain, dB	
max	60
min	9
Gain setting resolution, dB	1
Preamplifier gain, dB, not less than	40
Clock pulse repetition period, selectable	10, 30
Sweep generator period, selectable	10 s, 1 min, 1 h, 8 h
Maximum calibrator output voltage amplitude, V, not less than	
In continuous mode	1,6
In pulse mode	6
Calibrator RF pulse width range, μ s	45
Calibrator RF pulse fill frequency, kHz	300, 604
Threshold voltage for pulse and event generation, mV	106
Measurement range of AE pulse arrival time difference, μ s	8-800
Measurement error of AE pulse arrival time difference, μ s, no more than	1
Device threshold sensitivity to acoustic signal displacement amplitude, m	>5

a)

b)

Fig. 35. a) cylinder №1; b) 94636 events

a)

b)

Fig. 36. a) cylinder №2; b) 29025 events

a)

b)

Fig. 37. a) cylinder №3; b) 72110 events

Fig. 38. a) cylinder №4; b) 72110 events

Comparison of the distributions of events recorded over 10 seconds of the experiment. When the engine is idling, the main source of AE is the difference in pulse signals, indicating uneven fuel delivery to cylinders 2 and 3.

5. AE – diagnostics of fuel equipment and cylinder valves of a marine diesel generator

The research methodology for a diesel generator (4CH 8.5/11 16 kW Marine Diesel Generator) included installing piezoelectric transducers (PETs) on the engine injectors. The engine was idling at fixed values, at which various PE systems recorded PE signals during fuel delivery. The results were then analyzed to identify the sources of the acoustic signals.

PETs were mounted on the engine injector body symmetrically relative to the cylinders. From the PETs, signals generated by fuel delivery were sent through a preamplifier to PE devices for further amplification. When pressure in one of the lines increases, the sensor generates a pulsed signal, which is sent to the PE device. The PE signals characterize noise effects in the range of ultrasonic vibrations as fuel pressure in individual lines increases (the maximum pressure is 18 MPa) during one engine operating cycle. The cylinder firing order was determined by sequentially repositioning the fuel injection pump (HIPP) through the fuel lines. The maximum AE signal from cylinder 2 was recorded by various AE equipment.

The study concluded that the obtained AE signals are initiated by the fuel supply system. It is evident that the amplitude of the AE signal from cylinder 2 has changed and differs significantly from the normal fuel supply state to the other cylinders. Furthermore, the structure of the recorded signals reveals non-uniform fuel delivery to the cylinders, indicating differences in the operation of the high-pressure fuel pump sections.

Of particular interest is the study of AE signals from the operation of a single fuel injection section.

1 - AE signal from a single fuel injection section;

2 - pulse signal from the fuel injection pump (FEP) installed on the fuel injection line of cylinder 2.

It is evident that in the section from the beginning of the pressure increase to the moment of fuel injection into cylinder 3, the AE signal is characterized as "low-amplitude emission." In the section from the start of fuel injection into the second cylinder, the AE has an "explosive" character and remains for some time, although the pressure in the pipeline has already dropped.

Stage 1. Fuel System Diagnostics

Test time: 14 hours 20 minutes

The sensors are mounted on plates with magnetic holders.

Sensor №1 – mounted on the valve cover of cylinder №1

Sensor №2 – mounted on the valve cover of cylinder №4

Valve cover material – silumin.

Fig. 39. a) Installing sensors on the valve cover of cylinder №1 and on the valve cover of cylinder №4; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 1

Consecutive two waveforms for channel №2 (a) and channel №1 (b) relative to the measurement time.

Fig. 40. Waveform, first dimension a) cylinder №4; b) cylinder №1

Figure 12 (a) shows the time-delayed amplitudes of the AE signals from sensor 1, located on cylinder 4. Obviously, during normal cylinder operation, the signal amplitudes should be approximately the same at any given time. However, it is noticeable that the signal amplitudes during cylinder operation differ significantly. This indicates that the cylinder is operating unevenly, leading to increased fuel consumption and, consequently, increased environmental pollution due to incomplete combustion of the fuel supplied to the cylinder. The uneven operation of cylinder 1 is even more noticeable, shown in Figure 13 (b), which shows the changes in the AE signal amplitudes.

Comparison of the AE results from both cylinders also reveals uneven operation, indicating the need for their adjustment before scheduled maintenance.

Stage 2

Test time: 14 hours 31 minutes

The sensors are mounted on plates with magnetic holders.

Sensor №1 is mounted on the valve cover of cylinder №2

Sensor №2 is mounted on the valve cover of cylinder №3

Fig. 41. a) Installing sensors on the valve cover of cylinder №2 and on the valve cover of cylinder №3; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 2

Fig. 42. Waveform, first dimension a) cylinder №2; b) cylinder №3

Even greater unevenness is observed during the operation of cylinders 2 and 3, as shown in Fig. 3 (a – operation of the valves of the second cylinder) and 4 (b – operation of the valves of the third cylinder). Thus, it can be assumed that the operation of the diesel generator requires thorough adjustment during the next repair or, if possible, directly during operation.

Stage 3

Test time: 14 hours 39 minutes

The sensors are mounted with electrical tape.

Sensor №1 – installed between cylinders №1 and №2

Sensor №2 – installed between cylinders №3 and №4

Fig. 43. a) Installing sensors on the valve cover between cylinders №1 and №2 and between cylinders №3 and №4; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 2

Fig. 44. Waveform, first dimension a) between cylinders №1 and №2; b) between cylinders №3 and №4

The obtained result indirectly confirms the uneven operation of the piston group of diesel generator cylinders, and the nature of the data of similar measurements on each cylinder separately, which allows, when diagnosing the operation of a diesel generator, to limit measurements to positions between cylinders, which will reduce the amount of work, especially in operation

Stage 4.

Uniformity of fuel supply from the injector and operation of the fuel pump

Test time: 15 hours 32 minutes

The sensors are installed on the injector and fuel pump.

Sensor №1 is installed on the injector of cylinder №3.

Sensor №2 is installed on the fuel pump.

Fig. 45. a) Installing sensors on the injector of cylinder №3 and the fuel pump; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 4

Fig. 46. Waveform, first dimension a) injector №3; b) the fuel pump

The fuel pump (Fig. 46b) operates normally, but uneven fuel delivery from injector №3 (Fig. 46a) is visible. This uneven operation is clearly due to the piston assembly and injector operation.

Stage 5.

Uniformity of fuel supply by the fuel pump from the plunger of the 4th cylinder

The sensors are installed on the fuel line and on the fuel pump housing.
 Sensor №1 is installed on the fuel line of cylinder №4.
 Sensor №2 is installed on the fuel pump housing.

a)

b)

Fig. 47. a) Installing sensors on the injector of cylinder №4 and the fuel pump; b) Sensor installation diagram stage 5.

Stage 5.1

Test time: 15 hours 39 minutes

Both sensors are on

Stage 5.2

Test time: 15 hours 44 minutes

Only sensor №2 is on

Stage 5.3

Test time: 15 hours 49 minutes

Only sensor №1 is on

a)

b)

Fig. 46. Waveform, first dimension a) Operation of the plunger of the fuel pump of the №4th cylinder; b) the fuel pump

Based on the pipeline and pump system, it can be concluded that they operate quite smoothly and do not require adjustments until scheduled maintenance is completed.

AE diagnostics of the fuel system of a marine diesel generator

The graphs show uneven operation of the valve timing mechanism and fuel supply.

Fuel System Diagnostics Conclusions and Discussion

As a comparison of diagnostic results has shown, the portable AE POCKET device and other AE NDT systems are sufficient for express testing. They allow for assessing the uneven operation of key engine components, followed by identifying components requiring adjustment during basic stationary maintenance during scheduled repairs. However, some adjustments can also be made directly during operation.

Research has shown that the acoustic emission method allows for assessing uneven piston group operation and injector performance.

The AE method is suitable for diagnosing diesel engine fuel systems, primarily for assessing the uniformity of valves and injectors.

A distinctive feature of this method is the ability to conduct diagnostics directly during operation in real time, eliminating the labor-intensive and time-consuming disassembly and assembly of diesel engine components. A comparison of diagnostic results using the AE POCKET and the Vallen Systeme station showed that the portable AE POCKET device is sufficient for assessing the uneven operation of the main components of the engine fuel system, followed by identification of those requiring adjustment.

The use of the AE POCKET allows for the determination of the need for adjustment of fuel system components during operation, and, if possible, for adjustment before scheduled maintenance.

A distinctive feature of the proposed approach using the AE diagnostic method is the documented confirmation of the need for adjustment of engine fuel system components.

The main components that contribute to uneven engine operation are the piston groups of cylinders and injectors.

The need for uniform operation of fuel system components is as follows:

- fuel consumption savings
- environmental protection due to complete fuel combustion
- reduction of engine noise and vibration
- reduction of time, material, and human resources, due to a reduction in volume and possibly frequency of scheduled maintenance
- improving working conditions during operation.

Conclusions on injector operation

The nature of the AE change during loading mode has a specific pattern. In this case, the amplitude and energy are small and fluctuate within certain limits, reflecting the flow of fuel through the pipeline and the operation of the fuel pump. However, during normal fuel transfer, a significant jump in the AE level was recorded across all instruments, indicating abnormal fuel pump operation when delivering fuel to cylinders 2 and 3, indicating uneven fuel delivery to the injectors. The conducted analysis allows us to identify the main shortcomings of existing diagnostic methods for diesel engine units and minimize soot emissions, which occur when an internal combustion engine operates on diesel fuel, and particulate matter in the exhaust.

The following graphs of the AE signal (recorded in the channels of different AE systems) show a jump in fuel delivery to the injectors (injectors No. 2 and 3, Fig. 1) are presented.

1. The feasibility of effectively using AE for solving problems of functional diagnostics of piston diesel control systems is demonstrated.
2. The principles of functional AE diagnostics for piston diesel control systems are developed.
3. Some circuit solutions for the practical use of AE as a means of functional diagnostics of piston engines are presented.

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ADDITIONS

It follows that the inaudible sound of the valve mechanism is detected by the acoustic emission equipment, which corresponds to the processed signal graphs, requiring valve adjustment. Similarly, the uniformity of fuel delivery by the high-pressure pump is also evident from the graph, indicating uniform fuel delivery to the injectors.

If the valves are not adjusted promptly, compression problems may occur, leading to reduced power, unstable operation, and increased fuel consumption.

- Incorrect fuel combustion. If the clearances between the valves are too large or too small, the fuel will not burn completely. This can lead to poor fuel economy and increased emissions.

Increased fuel consumption. Due to incorrect valve operation, the fuel does not burn as efficiently as it should. This leads to increased fuel consumption, which not only impacts the budget but also the environment.

1. The potential for the effective use of AE for solving problems of functional diagnostics of piston diesel power units is demonstrated.

2. Principles [which principles? Describe! What diagnostic criteria do you use?] for functional AE diagnostics of piston diesel power units are developed.

3. Some circuit solutions for the practical use of AE as a means of functional diagnostics of piston engines are provided.

Comments:

This should be formatted according to the rules for formatting text documents.

This means: each drawing, diagram, and photograph must be captioned, with a description of what is depicted.

Reference

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Основные параметры АЭ системы Physical Acoustics Pocket AE:

количество АЭ каналов – 2,
количество плат обработки сигналов ASIP-2/S – 4,
разрядность АЦП -16 бит.

Плата обработки сигналов ASIP-2/S

Обработка сигналов	Описание
Аналоговые полосовые фильтры	0,5 или 18 кГц (выбирается переключателем) - 2,4 МГц (при ослаблении -3 дБ)
АЦП	АЦП 40 МГц при 16 бит на канал
фильтр нижних частот FIR:	Отсечка: 3.6 MHz (-6 dB) при 40 MSPS, 18 бит. Результирующая полоса пропускания с учетом аналогового и FIR -фильтра: 2,2 МГц (при затухании -3 дБ)
Цифровой фильтр для конкретного приложения	Полосовой фильтр, состоящий из нижних (LP) и верхних (HP) фильтров Баттерворта 8-го порядка каждый.
Затухание на спаде цифрового фильтра	48 дБ / октаву для LP и HP
Включенные цифровые фильтры	25 - 45 кГц, 25 - 300 кГц, 25 - 850 кГц, 50 - 300 кГц, 50 - 850 кГц, 95 - 300 кГц, 95 - 850 кГц, 230 - 850 кГц, байпас
Выбор цифрового фильтра.	Программный выбор для каждого канала индивидуально.

Стандарты и директивы

Директива по электромагнитной совместимости 2014/30/ EU

Стандарты EMC EN61326-1: 2013, EN61326-2-3: 2013, EN61000-6-2: 2006, EN61000-6-4: 2011

Стойка для ударов и вибрации. EN60068-2-6: 2008

Стандарт AE EN13477-1: 2011, EN13477-2: 2021

Тех. характеристики системы сбора и регистрации АЭ данных Physical Acoustics Pocket AE

Общие параметры	
Количество каналов	2
Длина сегмента кабеля для передачи данных между модулями АЭ	не более 2 м
Аналоговый тракт	
Коэффициент усиления (с шагом 1 дБ)	20 ÷ 60 дБ
Уровень шума, приведенного ко входу в полосе 30 ÷ 500 кГц	не более 5 мкВ
Частоты среза для переключаемых НЧ-фильтров	100, 250, 350, 500 кГц

Частоты среза для переключаемых ВЧ-фильтров	30 (1*), 50, 100, 150 кГц
Неравномерность АЧХ в диапазоне рабочих частот	+ 0,5/-3 дБ
Амплитуда импульсов в режиме излучения	10 ÷ 140 В
Частота излучаемых импульсов	1 Гц
Измерительный тракт	
Диапазон рабочих частот измерительного тракта	30 ÷ 500 кГц
Разрядность АЦП	14 бит
Частота преобразования АЦП	1 (2*) МГц
Динамический диапазон измерения амплитуды АЭ сигнала	не менее 72 дБ
Канал цифрового осциллографа	
Количество каналов цифрового осциллографа	1 на модуль АЭ
Частота дискретизации цифрового осциллографа	25, 50, 100, 250, 500, 1000 кГц
Измеряемые АЭ параметры	
Максимальная амплитуда АЭ сигнала	не менее 100 дБ
Погрешность измерения максимальной амплитуды АЭ сигнала	± 0,5 дБ
Динамический диапазон измерения энергии АЭ сигнала	не менее 120 дБ
Диапазон измерений числа выбросов АЭ сигнала	1 ÷ 32768
Диапазон измерений длительности АЭ сигнала с разрешением 1 мкс.	1 ÷ 65535 мкс
Диапазон измерений времени нарастания АЭ сигнала с разрешением 1 мкс.	1 ÷ 65535 мкс
Погрешность временного разрешения при регистрации АЭ сигнала по каналам	± 1 мкс
Программируемые параметры	
Диапазон изменения уровня отсечки шумов	0 ÷ 108 дБ
Диапазон максимальной длительности	10 ÷ 65535 мкс
Диапазон изменения тайм-аута длительности	10 ÷ 65535 мкс

Диапазон изменения «мертвого времени»	30 ÷ 65535 мкс
Параметрические каналы	
Максимальное количество параметрических каналов	4 на каждый модуль АЭ
Разрядность АЦП параметрического канала	12 бит
Полоса пропускания параметрического канала	0 ÷ 5 Гц
Погрешность измерения параметрического канала	± 5%
Условия эксплуатации модуля АЭ	
Температура окружающей среды	- 20 °С ÷ + 50 °С
Относительная влажность при температуре + 25 °С	не более 95%
Атмосферное давление	460 ÷ 960 мм рт. ст.
Условия эксплуатации системного блока компьютера	
Температура окружающей среды	+ 5 °С ÷ + 40 °С
Относительная влажность при температуре + 25 °С	не более 80%
Атмосферное давление	640 ÷ 790 мм рт. ст.
Электропитание	
Питание комплекса	~220 В ± 20%, 50 Гц ± 1 Гц
Потребляемая мощность одного модуля АЭ	не более 2 Вт
Потребляемая мощность комплекса (в 6-х канальном исполнении)	не более 100 Вт

Основные параметры АЭ системы Vallen Systeme :

количество АЭ каналов – 8,
 количество плат обработки сигналов ASIP-2/S – 4,
 разрядность АЦП -16 бит.
 Плата обработки сигналов ASIP-2/S

Обработка сигналов	Описание
Аналоговые полосовые фильтры	0,5 или 18 кГц (выбирается переключателем) - 2,4 МГц (при ослаблении -3 дБ)
АЦП	АЦП 40 МГц при 16 бит на канал
фильтр нижних частот	Отсечка: 3.6 MHz (-6 dB) при 40 MSPS, 18 бит.
FIR:	Результирующая полоса пропускания с учетом аналогового и FIR -фильтра: 2,2 МГц (при затухании -3 дБ)
Цифровой фильтр для конкретного приложения	Полосовой фильтр, состоящий из нижних (LP) и верхних (HP) фильтров Баттерворта 8-го порядка каждый.
Затухание на спаде цифрового фильтра	48 дБ / октаву для LP и HP
Включенные цифровые фильтры	25 - 45 кГц, 25 - 300 кГц, 25 - 850 кГц, 50 - 300 кГц, 50 - 850 кГц, 95 - 300 кГц, 95 - 850 кГц, 230 - 850 кГц, байпас (широкополосная опция, например, требуется для проверки системы, а также рекомендуется для тестера датчиков Vallen (VST)). Доступны дополнительные полосовые фильтры
Выбор цифрового фильтра.	Программный выбор для каждого канала индивидуально.

Данные датчика АЕ VS150-RIC

VS150-RIC - пьезоэлектрический датчик АЭ со встроенным предусилителем. Его частотная характеристика характеризуется пиком на частоте 150 кГц, где наблюдается резонанс. Он подходит почти для всех приложений АЕ и особенно подходит для проверки целостности металлических сосудов под давлением. Он имеет интегрированный усилитель с 34 дБ усиления и *поддерживает автоматическое тестирование датчика посредством импульсов самоконтроля.*

Параметры ПАЭ (датчиков) VS150-RIC

Frequency Range (fPeak) [kHz]	100 to 450
Power Supply [vDC]	28±2
Typ. Power [W]	0.56 / 2.5 @ Signal 0% / 100%
Integrated Preamplifier	Yes
Preamplifier Gain [dB]	34
Pulse Through	Yes
Operating Temperature [°C]	-40 to +85
Vibration – Sinus Sweep	2 Oct/Min, 5 to 50 Hz, 20G
Ingress Protection Rating	IP40
Size (D x H) [mm]	28.6x31.5

Weight [gramm]	81
Case Material	Stainless steel
Wear Plate	Ceramics
Connector type	BNC
Shield Cross-Talk [dB]	<80
Typ. Noise (max. 1/s) [dBAE Peak]	25.2 @ 95-300kHz
Typ. Noise [μ Volt RMS]	5.0 @ 95-300 kHz

Стандарты и директивы

Директива по электромагнитной совместимости 2014/30/ EU

Стандарты EMC EN61326-1: 2013, EN61326-2-3: 2013, EN61000-6-2: 2006, EN61000-6-4: 2011

Стойка для ударов и вибрации. EN60068-2-6: 2008

Стандарт АЕ EN13477-1: 2013, EN13477-2: 2013

Характеристики ПАЭ GT200 производства Global Test

Параметр	Ед. измерения	Значение
Тип	-	Резонансный, без усилителя
Коэффициент электроакустического преобразования	дБ отн. 1 В/м/с	> 60
Электрическая ёмкость	пФ	400 - 500
Температурный диапазон	°C	-40...+150
Материал корпуса		титановый сплав
Длина встроенного кабеля определяется при заказе, стандартная 0,5 м)	м	0,5
Масса (без кабеля)	г	15